

Supplementary Figure 1. Correlation matrices between comparisons of different datasets (bacteria-fungi, bacteria-metabolites, and fungi-metabolites) on wet materials.

A Bacteria-Fungal Correlations on Wet Gypsum

C

Bacteria-Fungal Correlations on Wet Plywood

D

Bacteria-Metabolite Correlations on Wet Gypsum

G

Fungi-Metabolite Correlations on Wet Gypsum

H

Fungi-Metabolite Correlations on Wet Mold-Free Gypsum

I

Fungi-Metabolite Correlations on Wet Plywood

J

Fungi-Metabolite Correlations on Wet MDF

